

Ni(II) IONINING IMMOBILLANGAN POLIMER LIGAND BILAN HOSIL QILGAN KOMPLEKSINING IQ-SPEKTROSKOPIK TAHLILI**Mukumova G. J., Turaev Kh. Kh., Kasimov Sh.A., Karimova N.J., Shopo‘latova M.****Termiz davlat universiteti, O‘zbekiston**

Dunyo miqyosida tanlovchan, samarali kompleks hosil qiluvchi sorbentlar olishda tarkibida azot, fosfor, oltingugurt bo‘lgan ligandlarni organik polimer va mineral matritsalariga immobillashga yo‘naltirilgan ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari olib borilmoqda. [1,2]. Ushbu ilmiy tadqiqot ishida ligandlarni immobillash asosida xelat hosil qiluvchi sorbent va uning ayrim metallar bilan hosil qilgan kompleksining IQ- spektri o‘ganilgan. IQ- spektri 1-rasmda keltirilgan, IQ-spektri natijalariga ko‘ra 3417,68 cm^{-1} sohada $\nu(\text{OH})$ guruhining valent simmetrik ν_s va 1452,40 cm^{-1} sohada deffarmatsion δ tebranish chastotasi hosil bo‘ldi. 3337,63 cm^{-1} va 1544,98 cm^{-1} sohalarda $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$ guruhning valent simmetrik ν_s va deffarmatsion δ tebranishlari hamda 1062,78 cm^{-1} sohada $\nu(\text{C-N-})$ guruhining valent ν tebranish chastotasi kuzatildi.

1-rasm. Ni(II) ni TKFL ligandi bilan hosil qilgan kompleksining IQ- spektri.

Jadval

TKFL ligandi va uning Cu (II), Zn(II), Ni(II)ionlari bilan hosil qilgan koordinasion birikmalarining IQ--spektrlaridagi yutilish chastotalari, cm^{-1}

Tebranish tasniflari	TKFL	TKFL+Ni(II)	s m - 1
$\nu(\text{OH})$	3395,94	3417,68	
$\nu(\text{NH})$	3207,62	3337,63	
$\nu_s(\text{CH}_2)$	2951,09	2927,94	
$\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_2)$	2833,43	2850,79	
$\nu(\text{C=O})$	1712,45	1654,92	
$\nu(-\text{COC=O})$	1150,20	1109,07	
$\nu_{as}(-\text{COO}^-)$	1240,23	1402,25	
$\nu(\text{C-N})$	1060,85	1062,78	
$\delta(\text{OH})$	1417,68	1452,40	
$\delta(\text{NH})$	1271,09	1544,98	
$\delta(\text{CH}_2)$	750,31	673,16	
$\delta(-\text{COO}^-)$	840,56	920,46	
$\nu(\text{C=S})$	1190,08	1319,31	
$\nu(\text{O-Me})$	-	650,47	

Shu bilan birgalikda 2927,94 cm^{-1} , 2850,79 cm^{-1} va 673,16 cm^{-1} sohalarda $\nu(\text{CH}_2)$ guruhining valent assimmetrik ν_{as} , valent simmetrik ν_s va deffarmatsion δ tebranishlar chastotasi hosil bo‘ldi. 1654,92 cm^{-1} va 1402,25 cm^{-1} sohalarda $\nu(\text{C=O})$ hamda $\nu(\text{COO}^-)$

guruhining valent assimmetrik ν_{as} tebranish shu bilan bir qatorda $920,46 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ sohada deffarmatsion δ tebranish chastotasi hosil bo'ldi.

Shuningdek $1319,31 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ sohada $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ guruhining valent simmetrik ν_s tebranishi va $1109,07 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ sohada $\nu(\text{COOC})$ guruhining valent ν tebranish chastotalari kuzatildi. $650,47 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ sohada yangi $\nu(\text{COONi})$ guruhining valent ν tebranish chastotasi hosil bo'ldi. Shu bilan birgalikda TKFL sorbentidagi ayni shu bog'larning tebranish chastotalari o'zarganligi aniqlandi.

1-jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, TKFL sorbentidagi $\nu(\text{NH})$ tebranish chastotasi va $\delta(\text{C}=\text{O})$ tebranish chastotalari nisbatan boshqa sohalarga siljigan. Karboksil guruhidagi $-\text{OH}$ yo'qolib O-Me bog' hosil bo'ldi Bundan quyidagicha xulosa qilish mumkin, TKFL sorbentidagi ikkilamchi amin va korbanil guruhlari metall ionining koordinatsiyalanishini ta'minlaydi va xelat xalqa hosil bo'ladi.

Adabiyotlar

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